

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GIS SOLUTIONS IN THE FIELD OF TRANSPORT OF PETROLEUM PRODUCTS (“OIL & GAS”), IN A NATIONAL COMPANY - PART OF THE LOCAL ENERGY ARCHITECTURE

Author(s)*: Elena Cristina ANGHEL (VLĂDESCU)¹, Cătălin Nicolae POPESCU ²
Position: PhD, Economist, Lawyer¹, Prof.univ.dr.habil.eng.ec.²
University: University Petrosani¹, Petrol Gas University Ploiesti²
Address: Petrosani, street University, no. 20, Romania¹, Ploiesti, Bucharest street, no. 39, Romania²
Email: Cristina.Vladescu@conpet.ro¹, cpopescu@upg-ploiesti.ro²
Webpage: <http://www.upet.ro/>, <http://www.upg-ploiesti.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The approach starts from the definition of GIS as a technology that allows the manipulation of geographic information (geospatial), in order to determine the future behavior of the equipment.*

Methodology/approach - *We will analyze the current situation, the factors that influence the effectiveness of maintenance management and we will calculate financial performance indicators.*

Findings – *Now, the Crude Oil Pipeline System is being monitored and operated largely by the SCADA system and there is no integrated computer application to centralize heritage, technical and operational information, including based on their geographical location.*

Research limitations/implications – *The SCADA system receives information from sensors installed on the pumps, but there is a limitation of the SCADA system in terms of history, so the possibilities for detecting abnormal behavior based on historical developments are limited.*

Practical implications – *To maximize the return on investment, we propose that the GIS system be integrated with operation, maintenance and intervention, resulting in an integrated and efficient system.*

Originality/value – *The implementation of a GIS system will contribute to increasing the efficiency of internal processes through fast access to data and real-time collaboration, anticipating problems and reducing the costs of operating and maintaining the infrastructure.*

Key words: *management, GIS, infrastructure.*

GIS systems and management of transport network infrastructures

In the oil & gas transportation sector, the use of GIS-type solutions has seen a sharp development, especially due to the opportunity to manage operational risks, especially through the management of causes that can lead to operational events (poor maintenance, lack of knowledge the exact characteristics of the infrastructure and the lack of tools that allow the analysis of the characteristics of the infrastructure in the geographical context of the environment that the infrastructure crosses, including: the impact of the characteristics (physical and chemical) of the soil, the identification of high-risk areas from the perspective of the potential for environmental damage and of the population etc.). This information, characteristic of the "pipeline integrity management" discipline, cannot be managed in the absence of an IT tool that allows recording and working with technical information attached but at the level of some linear pipeline sections and that also allows viewing the physical and chemical characteristics of soil, as well as the location context of the pipeline infrastructure (human settlements, the size of the potentially affected population, proximity to other networks that can either cause or be affected in case of operational incidents, the impact on the environment and the impact environment on the potential for aggravating the effects of an operational incident, etc.).

The management of the integrity of pipeline networks has seen particular development and awareness in recent years due to a general process of aging of pipeline networks worldwide.

Operational justification of the implementation of a GIS type system

To maximize the return on investment and the benefits of projects implementing geospatial information management solutions, these solutions must be integrated into the company's IT infrastructure. By integrating these solutions with those for operation, maintenance and response, an integrated system is obtained that effectively communicates and supports all stages of the planning, design, construction, operation, maintenance and incident response processes of an infrastructure operating company of transport.

Currently, even though ERP or maintenance activity management systems allow the management of the technical characteristics and history of infrastructure elements, and CAD systems allow the drawing of infrastructure elements, none of these systems can manage location information as a GIS system. ERP or maintenance management systems do not allow working with geographic (positioning) or linear coordinates and cannot attach a technical characteristic such as diameter or type of insulation, but only for a defined pipe section, between two points clearly determined by coordinates.

Similarly, it is not possible in an ERP system to geographically locate a work order in the sense that one can specify the linear coordinates between which a job was executed and then be able to retrieve that information, but this time by selecting of a certain map area (retrieval involving transformation from linear coordinates to spatial coordinates and vice versa). On the other hand, CAD systems operate with static files, where features and attributes cannot be attached to drawn elements, data structures cannot be created, and collaboration between multiple users is not possible.

Now, the National Pipeline Transport System (SNTT) is mostly monitored and operated through the SCADA system from a technological point of view, and there is no integrated IT application that centralizes heritage, technical and operational information, including based on their geographical location. Through SCADA, information is received from the sensors installed on the pumps, but there is a limitation of the SCADA system about history, so the possibilities of detecting abnormal behavior based on historical developments are limited. We believe that it would be very useful to be able to do a historical analysis to determine the future behavior of the equipment.

The implementation of a GIS system (the creation of a unified database of spatial and non-spatial objects and attributes and the existence of a programmable platform through which workflows and functionalities can be implemented) creates the opportunity for the subsequent implementation of software "tools" and functionalities that geospatial technology makes them available. International studies¹ have shown that a basic geospatial infrastructure has a cost-benefit ratio of 1:1. When the company continues the process of developing the geospatial solution through its integration with operations and maintenance elements, as well as with the integration of other specific work processes, then the cost-benefit ratio increases exponentially, to values that cannot be easily quantified, but which affect positively the whole organization.

By implementing integrated systems such as MIS (Management Information System) and GIS (Geographical Information System), respectively, the degree of risk associated with the operation of the infrastructure is lower than if there is no automatic management tool for these activities, and the confidence of investors in such a company and that it will not be affected by major operational incidents that influence its financial performance, is greater.

The recommended technical solution for the implementation of the GIS system within the company that operates SNTT consists of an enterprise-type GIS system. The proposed system will initially consist of two advanced desktop workstations as well as a client-server web application platform that will be used by the mass of users. The system will also include mobile applications that will allow both the input of data from the field and the visualization of infrastructure details.

The desktop workstations will be used for data retrieval operations from existing sources within the company (measurements available for the entire network, made within a previous measurement project, positioning information of the pipeline axis, component elements and of corrosion points obtained from smart earthworks, cadastral information from existing situation plans, technical schemes). Also, these

¹ See "The value of a Utility GIS - a whitepaper" published by GITA (The Geospatial Information & Technology Association).

workstations will be used for complex reporting, analysis and thematic mapping operations, using positioning informations and technical characteristics, maintenance history.

Figure 1: Evolution of the Cost-Benefit ratio of implementing a geospatial solution, depending on the level of implementation

The integration with the ERP system will allow the association of information on revisions and repairs to the relevant infrastructure elements, at the relevant points and the visualization of this information in the GIS environment, together with the rest of the technical information relevant to the selected network section. Thus, there will be a complete technical view of the state of the infrastructure and it will be possible to investigate the causes of the appearance of corrosion at certain points of the network. Integration with the information system for document management will allow attaching any document type element (text, picture, diagram, etc.) to an infrastructure element, as well as indicating the exact area of applicability of this document within the linear network elements (for example, will be able to attach a technical sheet for the pipe from which the pipeline is made only between two identified points, either by geographic or linear coordinates, and will be able to attach a picture exactly at the point on the pipeline route to which that picture refers).

The GIS system will also manage all the information regarding the properties of the company, in the sense of their identification, their exact positioning at the correct geographical coordinates and the centralized storage of all relevant documents (cadastre, etc.).

One of the additional workflows implemented within the GIS system is that of analyzing and issuing approvals for constructions carried out in the vicinity of pipelines. The system will allow both the retrieval of information regarding the properties where approvals are issued, as well as the making of measurements, the extraction of relevant sections from the detailed map of the area and the electronic management of all approval file documents. The information regarding the issued approval will be saved in the map and will be able to be viewed later by the OTC staff (pipeline route operator) or by other authorized personnel, who will be able to check compliance with the approval conditions in the computer system on the ground.

We also propose the implementation of a set of specialized functionalities for pipeline integrity management, which would allow:

- automatic identification of areas of the pipeline where there are integrity problems, automatic calculation of the maximum pumping pressure to ensure the safe operation of the pipeline and automatic calculation of the remaining life time (based on information automatically retrieved from the results of integrity inspections);
- the automatic proposal of some lists of investment works to remedy the integrity deficiencies found following the inspections;

- making detailed maps of the areas with integrity incidents, to allow their identification on the ground;
- the analysis of all existing data regarding the pipeline, aligned in a linear coordinate system, including the retrieval of information regarding integrity inspections and their history and estimation of the degree of corrosion evolution.

Proposed implementation strategy for the crude oil transportation infrastructure operating company

The proposed implementation strategy runs for 3 years and includes 2 investment stages with a duration of 1 year each, in years 1 and 3, respectively.

The first stage of the investment includes the purchase of software (licenses), completion of the necessary hardware infrastructure, purchase of the background map, configuration of the data model of the database, configuration and development of specific functionalities of the GIS system, including the mobile application for OTC and interfaces with IT systems existing (ERP and document management). Existing electronic information on the position and configuration of the pipeline network will be uploaded to the database, as well as information on a selected pilot pumping station for which the feasibility of the proposed data model will be demonstrated. The workflow for retrieving patrimonial cadastral information will also be configured, as well as the workflow for issuing notices within the Notice Service.

After the completion of the first investment stage, year two will be used to operate the new system and implemented functionalities for the purpose of populating the database and for the rest of the stations, as well as identifying opportunities to develop the system with new workflows, including other departments.

The second phase of implementation will take place in year three and will include the implementation of additional functionalities for the management and integrity analysis of the pipeline network. The tablet application for technical staff will be developed and new workflows will be implemented in the GIS system. We are considering integration with new IT systems, such as network loss detection, to pinpoint the exact location of loss points.

The GIS system is used for: property management (land, buildings); search and view equipment characteristics, technical documentation; view history of maintenance works; management of operational incidents; mobile applications for technicians in intervention teams; topology and network analysis; designing new investments; viewing information from external systems (financial, SCADA, maintenance management, industrial systems for historical analysis of sensor data).

Figure 2: Integration of GIS systems with other typical IT systems

The role of the GIS system in the IT infrastructure of the SNTT operating company

A series of opportunities to optimize the current way of working resulted from the interviews with the company's staff. The solution of some of these can be the subject of the implementation of a GIS system, but a general solution can only be obtained through a combination of technical measures (the implementation of other types of information systems), administrative and procedural.

Regarding the information available from smart godevils², we specify that they contain not only information about the location of the pipeline axis, but also additional information that can be used to automatically create in the GIS system network elements such as pipe, valve, elbow, teu, discounts. Information on the condition of the pipeline in terms of its integrity can also be retrieved automatically.

Figure 3: Typical application ecosystem

² This information is available for buried pipelines for which electronic pipeline integrity reports exist. For a correct understanding of the role of a GIS system, we consider it useful to present the typical ecosystem of IT applications.

Maintenance management; the nomenclature of causes, defects, repairs for each type of equipment; annual preventive maintenance plans, based on the entire list of equipment managed in the system, with automatic estimation of the necessary resources, personnel and costs are not available in the current ERP system, but are necessary and requested by the technical departments with which they had analysis interviews take place. We believe that a detailed analysis of the needs and specific requirements from the point of view of computerized maintenance management is necessary.

Costs and revenues generated by project implementation

The revenues generated by the project are related to savings in operating costs achieved following the implementation of the project (reductions in costs for the relevant personnel for the implementation of the project, reductions in expenses with maintenance activities, support, maintenance, savings generated by reducing expenses with breakdowns, with moving staff to ensure maintenance and carry out other current activities and greening/environmental protection expenses).

The incremental operational costs generated by the implementation of the project are operational costs necessary to implement the GIS system (phone, tablet subscriptions, PODS subscription), as well as maintenance costs (maintenance of GIS licenses stage I, technical support operation, maintenance for the licenses associated with the new investment – stage II). The investment costs were calculated based on realistic estimates that were based on offers from specialized suppliers, similar projects carried out in companies that manage infrastructures similar.

The costs have been estimated and framed in such a way as to achieve the capitalization of as large a proportion of the investment value as possible.

The breakdown of costs (without VAT) over the duration of the investment is as follows:

Total investment: 4,406,037.00 lei, of which:

year 1: 2,090,650.00 lei

year 2: 467,337.00 lei

year 3: 1,848,050.00 lei

Table 1. Performance indicators - financial analysis

Project indicator	Result value	Conclusion
INVESTMENT		
Internal rate of return (RRF/C)	12,48(>4%)	The project is financially profitable
Financial net present value (FNPV)	1.503.254	
Benefit-cost ratio	1,2	
Recovery period	approx. 3 years	

Table 2. Calculation of the Internal Rate of Financial Return of the Investment

Calculation of the Internal Rate of Financial Return of the Investment (lei)	Updated Total	Out of Date Total	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
TOTAL ENTRIES/ REVENUES	9063110	10864958	0	473594	957028	1451715	1910932	1989309	2024000	2058380
Operating income	9063110	10864958	0	473594	957028	1451715	1910932	1989309	2024000	2058380
Residual value	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL OUTPUTS COSTS	7559856	8303387	2091340	895137	2278610	607660	607660	607660	607660	607660
Operation and maintenance costs (including replacement costs)	3311217	3897350	690	427800	430560	607660	607660	607660	607660	607660
Total investment	4248639	4406037	2090650	467337	1848050	0	0	0	0	0
NET CASH FLOW	1503254	2561571	-2091340	-421543	-1321582	844055	1303272	1381649	1416340	1450720
Discount rate	4,0%		1,0000	0,9615	0,9246	0,8890	0,8548	0,8219	0,7903	0,7599
FNPV	1503254									
RIRF	12,48%									
Benefit-cost ratio	1,20									
Recovery period	approx. 3 years									

Conclusions

We appreciate that our involvement in the operational justification of the implementation of a GIS-type system, as being the feasible and efficient technical way of managing linear infrastructures for the companies that manage or operate such infrastructures, through the use of GIS-type technologies, will contribute to the achievement analyzes based on the data collected from the economic-financial and production systems, of the technical and operational aspects.

Geospatial infrastructure management solutions provide many benefits, such as increasing the efficiency of internal processes through rapid access to data and real-time collaboration, anticipating problems and reducing costs related to operational incidents, increasing efficiency and reducing overall infrastructure operation and maintenance costs.

The COVID-19 pandemic has involved many unknown parameters, most of which have a spatial dimension. Thus, spatial analysis and GIS could provide appropriate decision-making tools, predictive models, statistical methods and new reporting technologies for management, avoiding direct staff contact and providing opportunities for spatio-temporal analysis, geo-business, participatory GIS, Internet of Things (IoT), Location Based Service (LBS), Web Mapping, Satellite Image Analytics and Pipeline Integrity Management/Failure Management to minimize causality, limit incidence, establish effective communication, provide new approaches for business in isolation situations, telework, adaptive decision making.

References

Dhillon B. S.

2006

Maintainability, Maintenance, and Reliability for Engineers, <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420006780>

Dimitriu G.

2020

Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Blue Publishing House

Elangovan K.

2020

GIS, NEW INDIA PUBLISHING AGENCY- NIPA

Ilie G.

2019

Business tools. Project Management. The business plan. The feasibility study, Publisher: Universitara

Imbroane A.M.

2019

Geographic information systems. Data structures. vol.1, Cluj University Press Publishing House

Kennedy M.

2017

The Global Positioning System and ArcGIS, Publisher: Taylor & Francis

Mitchell A.

2020

The ESRI Guide to GIS Analysis, Volume 1: Geographic Patterns and Relationships, Publisher: Esri Press

Najafi M., Kulandaivel G.

2005

Optimizing Pipeline Design, Operations, and Maintenance in Today's Economy, 767–781, ASTM CONFERENCE

Nitu C.

2015

Geographic information systems in cartography and cadastre, University Publishing House

Nitu C., Tomoiaga T.

2016

Design and implementation of Geographic Information Systems, University Publishing House

Sreekanth P.D., Soam S.K., Srinivasa Rao Ch.

2020

Practical Manual for GIS, Publisher: Daya Pub. House

Pipeline Operation and Maintenance: A Practical Approach, Second Edition, ASME 2010, <https://www.asme.org/publications-submissions/books/find-book/pipeline-operation-maintenance-practical-approach-second-edition>

<http://www.conpet.ro/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Point.-3-Information-strategic-development-perspectives.pdf>